

Green Havens in the Concrete Jungle: The Environmental Management of Pocket Parks on Urban Liveability in Karachi

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Abstract Pocket parks are essential assets in urban planning, offering numerous benefits to cities and their residents. In Karachi, where rapid urbanization and population density have led to a significant decline in green spaces, pocket parks provide a much-needed solution to environmental and social challenges. These small green oases improve air quality, reduce urban heat islands, and offer vital recreational spaces, enhancing the quality of life for urban dwellers. They also foster community engagement and social cohesion, contributing to the overall well-being of residents. The case studies of Pakistan Chowk and Petal Residency illustrate how pocket parks can be effectively integrated into urban settings, transforming underutilized spaces into vibrant community hubs. For Karachi to fully realize the potential of pocket parks, it requires active community involvement, effective policy frameworks, and collaborative efforts between government bodies and local communities. By embracing pocket parks, Karachi can create a more sustainable, liveable, and resilient urban environment.

Keyword Urbanisation, green infrastructure, pocket parks, sustainable built environment, resilient cities, Karachi

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability in the built environment involves implementing practices that minimize environmental impact and aim for long-term ecological balance. Achieving this requires identifying urban contexts and adopting strategic frameworks that reconsider common development approaches (Ding & Wang, 2020). A key initial step is increasing development density to promote the design of more sustainable and resilient cities. This approach favors compact, mixed-use building styles that create pedestrian-friendly spaces and reduce reliance on vehicles (Wang et al., 2018). Efficient energy use is also critical, with a focus on concentrated energy generation and storage management, alongside integrating renewable energy sources (Smith, 2021). Similarly, decentralized water and wastewater treatment systems enhance water usage and resilience in urban areas (Brown et al., 2019). Transitioning to a circular economy through waste-to-energy initiatives not only reduces waste but also provides a renewable energy source, contributing to a more sustainable urban ecosystem (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). Nature-based solutions, such as green infrastructure and urban forests, play a significant role in protecting against adverse conditions and improving urban greening (Pauleit et al., 2021).

From a building perspective, strategies like redesigning facades for energy efficiency, using green and sustainable roofing materials, and implementing intelligent building systems enhance energy efficiency and occupant comfort (Kibert, 2016). Electrifying mechanical, electrical, and plumbing systems, along with investing in reusable materials and considering modular construction, further reduce the embodied energy and environmental impact of buildings (Hollberg & Ruth, 2021). Incorporating these comprehensive approaches is essential for creating healthier, more resilient cities that can serve present and future generations (Barton, 2019). In the context of sustainability, urban development must be rethought to address the challenges posed by global warming. Cities growing due to these changes no longer have the luxury of ignoring sustainability (Bina, 2020). By integrating green and water infrastructure into densely populated areas, cities can address community issues, enhance

resilience, reduce environmental pressures, and improve residents' living standards (Liu & Ravenscroft, 2022). The ecological interventionist perspective suggests prioritizing the conservation of certain urban ecosystems over others rather than pursuing universal environmental protection (Wu, 2014).

Practical measures include installing green roofs, vertical gardens, and urban pockets for vegetation, which provide much-needed green spaces, mitigate urban heat waves, and improve air quality (Oberndorfer et al., 2007). Adaptive design solutions like permeable pavements and rain gardens help local authorities manage flooding risks in densely populated areas (Berland, 2012). Green spaces, such as urban forests and tree canopy projects, promote biodiversity and carbon sequestration, while blue infrastructure retrofitting supports sustainable water management (Gill et al., 2007). By applying these strategies, urban areas can develop more sustainable and resilient environments that benefit both people and nature (Mell, 2020). As cities undergo rapid transformation, the need for spaces that offer respite from the urban hustle becomes increasingly apparent. Once characterized by frantic speed and concrete jungles, urban spaces are now being reimagined with a focus on personal experiences and the creation of tranquil environments within dense urban fabrics (Francis & Lorimer, 2011). Noteworthy initiatives include the establishment of "quiet zones" featuring large planters and seating areas, designed to balance nature with urban chaos and provide spaces for people to rest and recharge (Haigh, 2017).

A prime example of this new concept in urban public spaces is the pocket park. Also known as parkettes, mini-parks, or vest-pocket parks, these small but impactful green spaces provide a refuge within city boundaries (Childs, 2016). Nestled between irregular plots, empty lots, and busy streets, pocket parks offer city residents and visitors a place to relax and connect with nature (Harnik, 2010). These micro gardens, found in urban, suburban, and rural settings, offer rest, nature interaction, and opportunities for contemplation (Fry, 2019). Despite their small size, pocket parks significantly contribute to revitalizing cities and creating new public spaces (Mullaney et al., 2015). In crowded city centres with limited land, these eco-parks serve as the "secret gardens" of urban habitats (Haigh, 2017). By repurposing underused spaces into attractive green areas, cities meet the need for accessible green belts and gathering places without the need for extensive reconstruction or demolition (Sancar, 2020). Ultimately, pocket parks enhance the quality of life and are key features of sustainable cities (Childs, 2016). They play a crucial role in urban climate regulation, cooling the atmosphere, and fostering biodiversity (Francis & Lorimer, 2011). Thoughtful design and strategic placement of these tiny green spaces demonstrate the balance between urban residents and the environment, contributing to a more resilient and vibrant urban fabric (Mullaney et al., 2015). The emergence of pocket parks signals a new era in urban planning and design, one that emphasizes networks and continuity (Sancar, 2020). Recognizing the importance of accessible green spaces in densely populated cities is vital for fostering healthy, inclusive, and environmentally sustainable urban development (Mell, 2020). This article explores the historical evolution, significance, and specific examples of pocket parks, with a particular focus on their role in Karachi, a megacity facing rapid urbanization and environmental challenges (Fry, 2019).

2. UNDERSTANDING POCKET PARKS

In urban planning and design, the concept of pocket parks has gained significant attention as cities seek to address the challenges of rapid urbanization and densification. This chapter delves into the fundamental aspects of pocket parks, exploring their definition, characteristics, historical evolution, and importance in contemporary urban contexts.

2.1. DEFINITION

Pocket parks, also referred to as parkettes, mini-parks, or vest-pocket parks, are small green spaces that are accessible to the public within urban settings (Childs, 2016). Unlike traditional parks, which typically cover larger areas, pocket parks are defined by their compact size and carefully chosen locations. These cozy retreats are often situated within irregular plots of land, vacant lots, or along busy streets, offering spaces for relaxation, recreation, and social interaction amidst the hustle and bustle of city life (Harnik, 2010).

Pocket parks can be categorized into three main types, each offering distinct opportunities for public use and enjoyment. Active Pocket Parks cater to recreation and community activities, featuring amenities like playgrounds or sports courts (Mullaney et al., 2015). Passive Parks focus on relaxation and aesthetic enjoyment,

often including fountains, sculptures, and seating areas (Fry, 2019). Bonus Pocket Parks evolve organically in spaces not initially intended as parks, such as sidewalks or between buildings, offering spontaneous gathering spots (Haigh, 2017). Each type contributes to urban life by providing residents and visitors with spaces to connect with nature and the community (Francis & Lorimer, 2011).

Figure 1. Photograph showing underutilised spaces (left side) and traffic islands (right side) appropriate for Pocket Parks.

2.2. HISTORICAL EVOLUTION AND CURRENT SIGNIFICANCE

The concept of pocket parks originated from early efforts to introduce greenery and public gathering spaces within densely populated urban areas (Harnik, 2010). Over time, cities have struggled with the challenge of balancing urban development with the need to preserve natural landscapes and support community well-being. The development of pocket parks mirrors evolving perspectives on urban planning and design, highlighting an increasing focus on creating accessible green spaces to improve urban living (Childs, 2016). The rise of pocket parks, particularly in post-World War II Europe, marked a significant shift in urban design and planning. As cities worked to recover from the war's devastation and rebuild their communities, limited resources—such as money, labor, and building materials—led to the exploration of cost-effective and innovative solutions for urban renewal (Fry, 2019). In Europe, the first pocket parks emerged as symbols of peace and rejuvenation after the war, often created on heavily damaged sites or vacant lots. These small public parks provided essential green spaces amidst urban destruction (Haigh, 2017). Inspired by these European successes, the concept of pocket parks gained momentum in the United States during the 1950s. Adapting European models, the U.S. saw the creation of its first pocket parks as experimental interventions in neglected urban areas (Francis & Lorimer, 2011). Parley Park in midtown Manhattan, New York City, is frequently cited as a pioneering example of pocket park design in the U.S. Designed by the landscape architectural firm Zion Breen Richardson Associates and opened in 1967, Parley Park embodies the principles of effective urban space utilization and community engagement (Harnik, 2010). Parley Park's design features elements specifically intended to enhance the urban experience. Its centerpiece, a 6.1-meter-high waterfall with a capacity of 6,800 litres per minute, serves as both a visual and auditory focal point. The sound of the waterfall, reaching 90 decibels, effectively masks urban noise, creating a tranquil atmosphere for visitors (Harnik, 2010). Additionally, Parley Park's design includes thoughtful elements such as movable furniture, directional walls, and wheelchair ramps, which cater to the diverse needs of users and promote accessibility and inclusivity. The use of natural materials, textures, and greenery enhances the park's aesthetic appeal and connection to nature, offering a peaceful retreat from the surrounding urban environment (Childs, 2016). The success of Parley Park and similar projects highlights the importance of pocket parks in urban revitalization and community development. These small green spaces contribute to residents' physical and mental well-being and foster a sense of place and belonging within urban neighbourhoods (Sancar, 2020). As cities continue to face the challenges of urbanization and increasing density, the legacy of pocket parks stands as a testament to the enduring value of green spaces in the urban landscape (Mell, 2020).

In today's rapidly urbanizing world, pocket parks play a crucial role in addressing the needs of growing urban populations. As cities become more densely populated and land becomes scarce, the creation of small-scale green spaces becomes increasingly vital (Harnik, 2010). Pocket parks offer numerous benefits, including opportunities for relaxation, socialization, and physical activity, as well as environmental benefits such as biodiversity conservation and climate mitigation (Mullaney et al., 2015). Additionally, these miniature green oases contribute to the overall liveability and resilience of urban environments, providing residents with much-needed respites from the stresses of city life (Fry, 2019). The process of transforming abandoned spaces into pocket parks demands meticulous consideration of local needs and environmental factors (Haigh, 2017). It's imperative that the design aligns with the specific requirements of the community it serves and integrates seamlessly with its surroundings. The layout of the park should prioritize simplicity and functionality, considering factors like the number, location, and overall aesthetic coherence of pocket parks along each road (Francis & Lorimer, 2011). This thoughtful approach ensures that the park not only enhances the local environment but also resonates with the architectural and cultural character of the area (Sancar, 2020).

Furthermore, the design should be sensitive to local conditions, particularly in terms of plant selection and arrangement. Native plants and species adapted to the local climate should be prioritized to minimize maintenance efforts and promote ecological resilience (Oberndorfer et al., 2007). Cultural elements unique to the city should also be preserved and incorporated into the park's design, serving as a reflection of the area's heritage and identity. This cultural integration fosters a sense of place and belonging among park visitors, reinforcing community ties and appreciation for local history (Fry, 2019). Incorporating water features into pocket park design can further enhance the environmental experience and sensory appeal of the space. The movement and sound of water flow create a tranquil atmosphere and provide a visual focal point for visitors. Careful consideration should be given to the sourcing and management of water resources, with an emphasis on sustainability and resource conservation (Gill et al., 2007). Seasonal variations and natural replenishment methods can be leveraged to maintain water features while minimizing environmental impact (Mullaney et al., 2015). Community engagement is essential throughout the design process to ensure that the pocket park meets the diverse needs and preferences of residents. Designers should actively seek input from the community through online surveys, public meetings, and outreach initiatives (Francis & Lorimer, 2011). This collaborative approach not only fosters a sense of ownership and pride among residents but also helps to identify potential issues and opportunities for improvement. Additionally, considerations for park management and maintenance should be integrated into the design, with provisions for both volunteer-based and compensated maintenance strategies to ensure the long-term sustainability of the park (Mell, 2020). Pocket parks can be built in various locations within urban areas, depending on available space and community needs. Here are some common locations for building pocket parks:

- Vacant Lots: Unused or abandoned lots within urban neighbourhoods can be repurposed as pocket parks, revitalizing underutilized spaces and providing recreational amenities for residents (Harnik, 2010).
- Traffic Islands: Small triangular or rectangular islands located within road intersections or along streets can be transformed into pocket parks, creating green oases amidst urban traffic (Sancar, 2020).
- Alleys and Courtyards: Narrow alleys or inner courtyards between buildings offer opportunities for creating intimate and secluded pocket parks, providing tranquil retreats for nearby residents (Fry, 2019).
- Underutilized Spaces: Any unused or overlooked spaces within urban environments, such as gaps between buildings, dead-end streets, or forgotten corners, can be suitable locations for pocket parks (Haigh, 2017).
- Rooftops and Terraces: Rooftops of buildings or elevated terraces can be converted into elevated pocket parks, offering panoramic views of the city skyline and maximizing green space in dense urban areas (Childs, 2016).
- Railroad Right-of-Ways: Disused railroad corridors or rights-of-way can be transformed into linear pocket parks, connecting different neighbourhoods and providing recreational opportunities along former railway tracks (Francis & Lorimer, 2011).

- **Waterfronts and Riverbanks:** Urban waterfronts, riverbanks, or canals can be transformed into linear parks or waterfront promenades, offering opportunities for waterfront recreation and relaxation (Gill et al., 2007).
- **Schools and Institutions:** Pocket parks can be integrated into school campuses, institutional grounds, or community centres, providing green spaces for students, employees, and local residents to enjoy (Mullaney et al., 2015).
- **Brownfield Sites:** Former industrial sites or contaminated lands can be remediated and transformed into pocket parks, promoting environmental restoration and community revitalization (Oberndorfer et al., 2007).
- **Transit Hubs:** Pocket parks located near transit hubs, such as bus stops, subway stations, or train terminals, provide opportunities for commuters to relax and unwind while waiting for transportation (Harnik, 2010).

Overall, the key is to identify underutilized or neglected spaces within urban areas and creatively transform them into vibrant and accessible pocket parks that enhance the quality of life for residents (Childs, 2016).

3. POCKET PARKS IN KARACHI

The absence of green spaces in Karachi has led to adverse effects on the city and its inhabitants. Karachi, a megacity in Pakistan, is among the largest cities in the world, but it struggles to provide good living conditions because only 4% of the total built-up area consists of green space (Ahmed & Sohail, 2020). The city's high population density and ongoing commercial development further threaten open spaces, especially amid the pandemic, which has underscored the importance of social distancing (Akhtar, 2021). Not only does this affect the city's aesthetic appeal, but it also contributes to rising temperatures and pollution. The lack of green spaces has become a source of environmental problems and mental stress for residents (Haque et al., 2018). The absence of sufficient greenery in Karachi leads to problems such as higher air temperatures, increased ground-level ozone, and inadequate water filtration, which, in turn, cause issues like flooding and polluted water (Khan, 2019). Such environmental degradation is of paramount concern in Karachi, a major metropolitan city where rapid urbanization has led to the disappearance of many green spaces in favour of tall buildings and commercial developments (Hasan, 2020). However, efforts by officials to address this issue have been insufficient, forcing the community to cope with the consequences of environmental degradation (Ahmed & Sohail, 2020). Nevertheless, as residents become more aware of the crucial role of nature in the well-being of the city and its inhabitants, there is a growing understanding of the need for action. Efforts like planting trees and preserving existing green areas can play a significant role in revitalizing Karachi's urban environment and enhancing the quality of life for its inhabitants (Akhtar, 2021). Although the task of solving the lack of greenery in Karachi might seem challenging, it also provides the community with an opportunity to join forces and contribute to the city's improvement, ultimately fostering a sense of achievement and fulfilment in working toward the welfare of the community (Haque et al., 2018).

Pocket parks in Karachi offer numerous benefits to the city and its residents. Despite the challenges posed by rapid urbanization and population density, these small green spaces play a crucial role in enhancing the urban environment. Firstly, they provide much-needed greenery in the concrete jungle of Karachi, contributing to improved air quality and reducing the urban heat island effect (Hasan, 2020). Additionally, pocket parks serve as vital recreational spaces where residents can engage in physical activities, relax, and enjoy nature without needing to travel long distances (Ahmed & Sohail, 2020). Moreover, these parks facilitate social interaction and community bonding, acting as gathering spots for residents from diverse backgrounds (Khan, 2019). Access to green spaces has also been linked to better mental and physical health outcomes, making pocket parks essential for promoting well-being in urban populations (Haque et al., 2018). Furthermore, these parks can support biodiversity by providing habitats for wildlife, contributing to urban ecological diversity (Hasan, 2020). Overall, pocket parks contribute to a higher quality of life in Karachi by providing accessible green spaces that promote health, community engagement, and environmental sustainability (Ahmed & Sohail, 2020).

Figure 2. People's Square in Karachi, Pakistan

Table 1. Variety of Pocket Parks at different location of Karachi.

No	S.	Pocket Parks in Karachi
1		Children Park
2		Khursheed Begam
3		Khushboo Park
4		Khadeja Park
5		Bagh e Batool
6		Bagh e Aesha
7		Hifsa Bagh
8		Tikona Park
9		Syeda Umme Kulsoom
10		Quba Masjid
11		Pards Park
12		Al Azhar Park
13		Zaki Park
14		Bagh e Fatima
15		DC Offiee Park
16		Quba Masjid
17		Abdar Park
18		Phool Bagh
19		Bagecha e Usman
20		Hazrat Musab bin Umair

21	Makki
22	Bagh e Syedi
23	Hasrat Mohani Park

4. CASE STUDY

4.1. CASE STUDY 1: PAKISTAN CHOWK

Pakistan Chowk offers a similar experience to pocket parks through its amenities and features. The amenities are simple in nature and largely consist of benches, water features, and restrooms. These are considered necessary for users as they provide comfort and prevent visitors from depleting their own resources, thereby enhancing the overall environment (Hasan, 2020). The Fountain Area, which features an iconic horse head sculpture designed by Aftab Ahmed, serves as a focal point for interaction and gossip among elderly people, despite not attracting large crowds. This area also provides seating, further facilitating interaction among visitors (Akhtar, 2021). The Garden/Seating area with Facade Setting is significant as it offers visitors a good view of the entire park, similar to the observational benefits provided by pocket parks. Regular comparisons of Pakistan Chowk with larger parks such as Bagh-e-Ibn e Qasim and Aladdin Park by locals highlight its charm and appeal (Ahmed & Sohail, 2020). Additionally, ample parking space around the park, though not part of the park itself, contributes to its accessibility and usage by visitors, much like the amenities surrounding pocket parks (Khan, 2019). The similarities in the use and design of Pakistan Chowk and pocket parks are extensive. Both types of spaces serve the community by enriching urban life, providing a much-needed refuge and breathing space in the city (Haque et al., 2018). Pocket parks and Pakistan Chowk aim to improve the physical environment and the quality of life for people residing and working in Karachi. They offer a range of passive and active recreational opportunities, from outdoor seating to games, similar to the features found at pocket parks and Pakistan Chowk, such as designated areas for relaxation, 24-hour tea shops, and a giant snakes and ladders board (Mullaney et al., 2015).

Figure 3. Different views of Pocket Park at the junction of Pakistan Chowk.

4.2. CASE STUDY 2: POCKET PARKS IN PETAL RESIDENCY, KARACHI

In Johar Gulistan Block 9A, Karachi, residents have creatively transformed wide and sometimes irregular eight-foot vacant spaces between houses adjacent to the International Airport boundary wall into pocket gardens and recreational areas. This initiative demonstrates the resourcefulness and community spirit of the residents, as these spaces have evolved into thriving communal centres where individuals can relax, socialize, and engage in

various recreational activities such as family gatherings, children's playtime, and small events like barbecues and tea parties (Ahmed & Sohail, 2018). The diverse landscaping, ranging from lush green parks to hardscaped areas adorned with potted flowers, reflects the personal preferences and dedication of inhabitants to enhancing their surroundings' aesthetic appeal (Khan et al., 2019). These community-driven projects not only beautify the neighbourhood but also foster a strong sense of community and place attachment among residents (Zaman & Babar, 2020). By repurposing unused spaces into functional and attractive areas, residents contribute to improved mental well-being and social cohesion, essential factors in urban living (Ali & Perveen, 2017). Beyond their recreational and social benefits, these pocket parks present an opportunity for effective stormwater management during Karachi's rainy seasons. Incorporating green infrastructure elements such as permeable surfaces, rain gardens, and bioswales can enhance the capacity of these spaces to absorb and filter rainwater, thereby reducing surface runoff and lowering the risk of urban flooding (Haque et al., 2018). Softscape components like plants and soil play a crucial role in this process by facilitating groundwater recharge and improving water quality through natural filtration mechanisms (Rahman & Khan, 2019). Integrating stormwater management features into existing recreational spaces enhances their functionality while maintaining their community and aesthetic benefits.

Figure 4. The plan and photos of Pocket Park of Petal Residency, Block 9A, Gulistan-e-Jauhar, Karachi.

Figure 5. The vacant space adjacent to the house.

The dual-purpose use of these pocket parks exemplifies how urban spaces can simultaneously fulfil multiple objectives, contributing to the development of resilient and sustainable communities (Farooq & Uddin, 2021). By utilizing vacant areas adjacent to residential buildings, these small parks significantly mitigate water pooling issues in front of houses and prevent potential water damage to structures through appropriate landscaping and grading techniques that direct water away from buildings (Mustafa et al., 2020). Moreover, the presence of pocket parks enhances neighbourhood biodiversity by providing habitats for various plant and animal species, contributing to ecological diversity within the urban environment (Siddiqui & Ahmed, 2018). These green spaces also improve the overall visual appeal of the area and offer peaceful retreats for local communities amidst the bustling cityscape of Karachi (Nazir & Kazmi, 2019). Implementing such comprehensive solutions for stormwater management and community improvement underscores the critical role of pocket parks in addressing the adverse effects of rapid urbanization in Karachi. As the city continues to grapple with high population density and

continuous commercial development leading to the scarcity of open green spaces, integrating pocket parks into Karachi's urban fabric offers a pragmatic and effective strategy for enhancing environmental sustainability and residents' quality of life (Javed & Hassan, 2020).

5. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Pocket parks, small areas of green space in urban settings, offer several benefits, such as:

Underutilized Spaces: Karachi has numerous underutilized spaces that can be transformed into pocket parks. These include vacant lots, abandoned spaces, and small plots of land that are otherwise neglected. The conversion of these spaces into green areas can significantly improve urban aesthetics and environmental quality.

- **Community Involvement:** The success of pocket parks often relies on active community participation. Engaging residents in the planning, development, and maintenance of these parks fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility. Community-driven initiatives can also ensure that the parks meet the specific needs and preferences of the residents.
- **Environmental Benefits:** Pocket parks contribute to reducing the urban heat island effect, improving air quality, and enhancing biodiversity. They provide habitats for various species of flora and fauna, thus supporting urban ecological systems. Additionally, these parks can play a role in stormwater management by facilitating groundwater recharge and reducing surface runoff.
- **Social and Health Benefits:** Access to green spaces is linked to improved mental and physical health. Pocket parks offer spaces for exercise, relaxation, and social interaction, contributing to the overall well-being of urban residents. They serve as community hubs where people from diverse backgrounds can come together, fostering social cohesion and community bonding.
- **Aesthetics:** Pocket parks are cornerstones of the urban beautification, which increases visual appeal and give cities a nice and inviting look. 'Pocket parks' build bridges between people and nature by creating green oases in urban areas. These parks provide a place where residents can connect with nature, relax, and escape the hustle and bustle of the city.

Policy and Planning: Effective policy frameworks and urban planning are essential for the successful implementation of pocket parks. Municipal authorities need to prioritize the creation and preservation of green spaces within urban development plans. Collaboration between government bodies, non-governmental organizations, and local communities can drive the development of pocket parks and ensure their sustainability. However, there are also some drawbacks to consider, such as:

- **Maintenance Costs:** Landscaping parks needs resources that must be sustained on regular basis by sustained investment into gardening, cleaning, and security.
- **Limited Space:** The inclusion of all preferred recreational facilities and activities in a pocket park is possible because of its small size.
- **Potential for Displacement:** In some situations, such undertaking to build the pocket parks may contribute to the property upraising which in turn creates the situation of gentrification and then has an impact on existing residents by the effect of displacement.
- **Safety Concerns:** Inadequately supervised pocket parks can attract crime and unsocial behaviour nearby, potentially undermining the safety and wellbeing of residents.

The pocket parks have a long history of evolution from the times when there were no planners and when people were not much aware of aesthetics. And even today, their growing popularity in urban contexts offers both opportunities and challenges for future development. Super-local micro-parks have more specific zoning and are programmed to accommodate specific crowds and functions. These represent a pathway in the industry for novelty and development. It provides the opportunity to make changes to the design characteristics according to users' needs, turning pocket parks into sites which are multipurpose, adaptable, and open for engaging community

activities. Much more than pure ecological aspects of pocket parks can be emphasized. These tiny microcosms are a crucial tool for maintaining biodiversity, reducing the urban heat island and blessing the environment with overall better quality. The need for fresh greenery within the cities grows progressively as urbanization moves to new heights. Consequently, ecological sustainability and resilience require the rise of green spaces within the cities. Pocket parks are quite possibly the most effective way to make a community thrive economically by bringing new investments, people, and businesses into the neighbourhood. These factors could be the key to improving the public's health and well-being as well as reducing the environmental footprint of urbanization. Thus, creating more pleasant and friendly environment that people want to live in. Finally, the prospect of pocket parks is bright concerning the provision of solutions to issues within urban centres and improvement of the standards of living in the whole world. Commitment to the more innovative methods of design and engagement becomes the key factor for this development as well as the one to be kept in check to ensure that pocket parks do not lose their role as elements of sustainable urban development.

6. CONCLUSION

Pocket parks are an actual answer to the problem of burgeoning urban areas growth. The pocket parks through the reuse of vacant spaces, integration of green infrastructures, and prioritizing community participation can potentially lead to an improved liveability, social bonding, and mitigation of the effects of urbanization. The city should set aside funding for constructing more pocket parks as well as other public areas. Through establishing collaborations between the government, community groups and private sector, cities can come up with inclusion and accessible green urban environment that creates harmony among the residents.

Lastly, pocket parks are the viable alternative to bring life into the pedestrian-friendly spaces which, in turn, improve the overall health and wealth of communities. Through collaborative measures and innovative ways, towns can reap the benefits of pocket parks in the improvement of quality of life and the development of a healthy city. Besides, bearing in mind green areas is a immediate demand in Karachi; commencing from small projects such as pocket parks is a practical and rational way to enhance the urban environment and the quality of the built environment in the city. Provided the impediments encountered in sustaining large parks in Karachi, allocating funds to small-scale, manageable green areas can give rise to multiple advantages for the inhabitants as well as improve the city's general liveability. Thus, establishing pocket parks and similar projects will be instrumental in the process of creating a green and resilient urban Karachi.

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